

ANALYSIS OF WORDS IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

G'iyos Do'stmurodov

Associate Professor, (PhD) University of Economics and Pedagogy

Mohinur Shokirova

1st year student at the University of Economics and Pedagogy

Annotation: This article identifies borrowings regarding the letter "N" in the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" published in 2022 and provides an opinion on which languages they came from. The article also presents a statistical analysis of borrowed words.

Key words: borrowings, linguistics, dictionary, term, dictionary types, terms, derivation.

The Uzbek language is a language that has come a long way in history and has a rich cultural heritage. After all, as our first president I.A. Karimov noted, "We need to preserve our native language, passed down from our ancestors, constantly strive to enrich it, and increase its prestige. It is especially necessary to expand the scope of our native language in such important areas as fundamental sciences, modern communication and information technologies, and the banking and financial system. The study of terms and expressions, in a word, the comprehensive development of the Uzbek language on a scientific basis, undoubtedly serves such noble goals as understanding national identity and a sense of homeland." Lexicography (or lexicology) is a branch of linguistics that studies words in a language, their meanings, structure, historical development, and relationships to them. Lexicography is mainly a systematic description of words and their meanings in a language. This discipline plays an important role not only in linguistics, but also in various scientific fields related to history, culture, and social life. The development of lexicography has undergone many major changes in the historical

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process. The development of artificial intelligence and language processing technologies has brought lexicography to a new level.

The evolution of language, the new meanings of words, and the interaction between cultures are adding new dimensions to modern lexicography. Words are used not only as a means of communication, but also as a means of social identification and preservation of cultural heritage. A dictionary reflects a language, a nation, its history, culture, and worldview. Therefore, lexicography is a unique scientific activity and is considered an important tool for understanding the development and change of language. The history of lexicography is an important way to study how words have developed in a language and how they have interacted with social life. This field helps to understand not only the changes in words in a language, but also the structure of their meanings and their place in society.

The famous French writer A. France, while talking about dictionaries, said, "A dictionary is a treasure placed in alphabetical order. If we think about it better, a dictionary is a book of books. It opens the way to all other books..." Dictionaries are distinguished among scientific linguistic literature by their invaluable service in ensuring interlanguage relations, studying the grammatical structure of the language, establishing language norms, cultivating the national thinking and speech richness of members of society, cultivating the national thinking and speech richness of members of society, forming socio-political consciousness, as well as increasing the effectiveness of education.

Since its inception, language has been fulfilling the function of forming and developing human thinking. This serves to enrich the vocabulary of our language. The richness of the vocabulary increases as a result of creating words based on internal possibilities and adopting words from other languages. These, in turn, create the own layer and the adopted layer of the vocabulary of the language. Along with internal possibilities, adopted words are also of great importance in the enrichment of the Uzbek lexicon. The entry of words from foreign languages into our language and their use leads to the appearance of a certain word in our language, such words

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are considered adopted words. As a result of contact with other languages, the Uzbek language has received many scientific, economic, technical, and cultural adoptions. In particular, several words from European languages have entered it along with new concepts: optimistic, negative, normative, navigation, notary, numismatics, headphones, novella. All this expands the lexical possibilities of the Uzbek language. The granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language and the achievement of the Uzbek people's freedom and independence have further accelerated this process, and thousands of neologisms have appeared in our language.

Neologisms are a collection of words from the Greek, neos - new, logos - word, and are words that express new things and concepts that have emerged with the needs of social development. Neologisms initially seem like unusual words, but due to frequent use, they lose their novelty and become active words, form part of the dictionary, and have an explanation. An explanatory dictionary is one of the types of linguistic dictionaries. In it, firstly, the meaning of each word (head word) included in the dictionary is determined and recorded, and if it has multiple meanings, its meanings are determined and recorded. Secondly, this meaning is explained, that is, it is explained, recorded in a descriptive way. The “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” published in 2020 consisted of 5 volumes in Cyrillic script, while the 2022 edition consists of 6 volumes, including about 5,000 new words (more than 80,000 words in total). The Explanatory Dictionary was prepared in cooperation with the Uzbek Language Development Fund under the Cabinet of Ministers, the Academy of Sciences, and the Gafur Ghulom Publishing and Printing House. The scientists - Academician Azim Hojiyev, Academician Tora Mirzayev, and Academician Ernest Begmatov - participated in the preparation of the first volumes of the Explanatory Dictionary.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language”, loanwords were assimilated across languages as follows:

T/r	Language of origin	Number of words
1	Persia	156
2	Arabic	120
3	Latin	33
4	Greek	15
5	Arabic-Persian	15
6	English	10
7	Russian	10
8	French	5
9	Italian	3
10	Turkish	2
11	Spanish	2
12	Persian -Arabic	2
13	German	2
14	Mongolian	1

Can loanwords be divided into the following thematic groups?

- 1. Persian.** The loanwords from this language have become so deeply embedded in our language that we can hardly distinguish them from Persian. Most of them relate to the natural, social, and scientific spheres. *Nargis, na'matak, nafarmon, namreza, namozshomgul.* **Namozshomgul** – is a flower that blooms in the evening. A perennial and annual herbaceous plant that blooms in the evening and closes in the morning, and its flowers are white, yellow, or red.
- 2. Arabic.** Arabic borrowings are mainly due to the Arab conquests, the widespread spread of Islam, the teaching of Arabic script in madrasas, and the fact that scholars created in Arabic. For example, *nahrullhayot, nas'taliq, nasroniy, nabi.* **Nabi** – a prophet, a bringer of divine messages. Conveying the will of Allah to the servants; a prophet. Prophets, messengers, and geniuses are in it, Tombs and palaces are in a row.
- 3. Latin.** Latin borrowings are mainly related to chemistry and medicine. For example, *natriy, neodim, nigrol, novokain, neon, niobiy.* **Niobiy** – [named after the daughter of Tantalus in Greek mythology – the princess of Thebes, Niobe (niobe)]

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is a chemical element belonging to group V of the Mendeleev periodic system; a hard-to-melt, corrosion-resistant gray metal.

4. **Greek.** Greek borrowings are mainly related to chemistry and are also widely used in everyday life. For example, **naftalin**, **nitro** – [nitron - saltpeter, soda] indicates a connection with nitrogen, nitric (nitric) acid: nitrates, nitroglycerin.

5. **Arabic+Persian.** Arabic+Persian words are mainly related to the field of biology. For example, **nabototshunos** (botanist) – a person who studies plants; a.k.a. botanist.

6. **English.** English borrowings are mainly related to science and technology. For example, neylon, novella, **noutbuk** [notebook- notebook; notebook]. A portable personal computer, usually resembling a small flat suitcase, with capabilities comparable to regular personal computers and capable of connecting to the Internet.

7. **Russian.** The words borrowed from Russian are mainly related to technology. For example, **naushnik** (earphone) - a device that is worn on the ear. A device that allows you to listen to messages transmitted via a walkie-talkie or telephone; a headset. The major decided to land the planes himself by giving the command via the walkie-talkie, so he took the earphone from Rusanov and listened.

8. **French.** The French borrowings are mainly related to law. For example, **naturalizatsiya** (naturalization) [naturalis - true, legal]. The admission of a foreigner to the citizenship of a certain state; the right of a foreigner to such a status.

9. **Italian.** Italian borrowings are mainly related to literature. Novelist, novella - novelty. A small genre of prose, a short story. Abdulla Qodiriy not only founded the satirical novella in Uzbek literature, but in the 1920s he was one of the first to write two major novels - "Days gone by" and "Scorpion from the Altar".

10. **Spanish.** Spanish borrowings are mainly related to the animal world. For example, **nutriya** is a rodent that lives in water and is raised and bred on farms for its valuable fur. Mo‘ynachilik fermalarida yaqin-yaqingacha nutriyat boqish va uni ko‘pytirish yaxshi yo‘lga qo‘yilmagan edi.

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11. German. Germanic borrowings are historical. For example, **neandertal** (Neanderthal) [from the Neanderthal Valley (Germany), where primitive human remains were first excavated (1856)] An ancient fossil human species that occupied a place between Pithecanthropus and modern man in the evolutionary development of humanity. Neanderthals found in Asia, Central Asia and Africa were not very tall.

12. Turkish. Turkish borrowings are mainly geographical. For example, **neft(oil)** najdak - a rock consisting of small and thin, granular crystals.

13. One word has been borrowed from **Mongolian** into Uzbek, which is related to the military field. For example, navkar [nokhor - friend, comrade; husband] a military servant, soldier. Husayn Bayqaro “Bog‘i Shimol” darvozasi yaqinidagi.... Chodir ichida ikki-uch navkari bilan o‘tirardi.

In conclusion, it can be said that today, along with the times, the words in our speech are becoming more modern. Neologisms appear with the needs of society and the times and take on a permanent character in their use, contributing to a significant increase in the vocabulary of a language.

References:

1. I.A.Karimov. “Yuksak ma’naviyat – yengilmas kuch”. –Toshkent, 2008.
2. “O‘zbek tili izohli lug‘ati”. – Toshkent, 2020-yil (5 jildli)
3. “O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati”. –Toshkent, 2023-yil. (6 jildli)
4. NNabiyeva N. “O‘zbek tili leksikasining tarixiy bosqichlari”. Humanities and Social Sciences 2022.
5. “ O‘zbek tili leksikologiyasi “.–Toshkent, 1981.
6. “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” . –Toshkent, 2006.
7. Avdiev V.I. “Qadimgi sharq tarixi”.1993-yil. B.130.

